

Graphical Abstract

Extension of the consistent δ^+ -SPH model for multiphase flows considering the compressibility of different phases

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Highlights

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- The consistent δ^+ -SPH model is extended to simulate the multiphase flow problems.
- The present multiphase model improves both the stability and accuracy of multiphase interfaces without background pressure.
- The present SPH model accurately predicts the compressibility of gas.
- The proposed SPH model is validated through six benchmarks including violent impact scenarios.

Extension of the consistent δ^+ -SPH model for multiphase flows considering the compressibility of different phases

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Abstract

In hydrodynamic problems involving wave impact on structures, air compressibility is crucial for accurate pressure prediction when an air bubble is entrapped. In this work, the consistent δ^+ -SPH model, originally developed for single-phase scenarios, is extended to multiphase contexts. Although the consistent δ^+ -SPH model shows good performance for single phase and viscous flow simulations, extending it to multiphase scenarios presents challenges, such as proper implementation of particle shifting for multiphase interfaces. Therefore, within the framework of the consistent δ^+ -SPH, we introduce the following enhancements: firstly, new strategy for handling $\delta\mathbf{u}$ -terms given by the particle shifting technique at multiphase interfaces are proposed to maintain stability and conservation. Secondly, for modeling of incompressible phases, like water, an acoustic damper term is introduced to alleviate acoustic waves resulting from the weakly-compressible assumption, which is expected to achieve smooth pressure field comparable to truly-incompressible hypothesis, thereby reducing the nonphysical pressure wave during the violent impact state; for modeling compressible phases like air, a physical sound speed is adopted in the equation of state to accurately model real gas phase compressibility. To test and validate the present multiphase SPH model, simulations were conducted for six scenarios. In particular, except for sloshing with two-layer liquids, the other scenarios fully consider air pressure oscillations when air is entrapped, compressed, or expanded by surrounding flows. The results demonstrate significant advantages of the present SPH model in simulating multiphase problems involving strong liquid impact and different phase compressibility.

Keywords: Multiphase, Particle shifting, δ^+ -SPH, Compressible flow

1. Introduction

The study of multiphase flows is essential in both scientific and engineering domains, attracting significant attention from scholars in recent years [1, 2]. Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) has emerged as a valuable approach for studying multiphase flow problems. However, due to the unavoidable discontinuous characteristics such as density, and physical interactions at the phase interfaces, Eulerian mesh-based methods face inherent challenges. In this regard, Lagrangian particle methods stand out for their ability to handle complex interfaces and multiphase flows with deformations without requiring additional numerical treatments for interface tracking [3–6]. Among these methods, Smoothed Particle Hydrodynamics (SPH) is extensively applied in simulating multiphase flows [7–13].

Previous studies on multiphase flow models, such as water-gas phase models, often assume that both water and gas are incompressible, as seen in VOF-based methods (see e.g., [14]) and level-set methods (see e.g., [15]). However, in scenarios involving violent free surface flows, such as wave impacts on structures or sloshing, air entrainment or water-air mixing can lead to compression and expansion of the air phase, resulting in pressure changing rapidly and with long-term oscillation [16–19]. Hence, it is crucial to consider the compressibility of different phases when studying such multiphase flow problems.

Multiphase SPH schemes can be categorized according to how pressure is solved, leading to two main approaches: Weakly Compressible SPH (WCSPH) [20, 21] and Incompressible SPH (ISPH) [22–24]. In the WCSPH framework, the pressure is explicitly solved based on the Equation of State (EOS), making it well suited for compressible multiphase flow problems, while the ISPH model solves the pressure implicitly via the Poisson equation, which poses challenges for handling strongly compressible flows [25–27]. Additionally, the ISPH scheme also faces difficulties in parallelization [28], while the WCSPH scheme is well suited for multi-GPU simulations [29]. In this study, the WCSPH scheme is chosen because of its ability to handle the compressibility of fluid phases while naturally satisfying the free surface condition [30].

Within the context of WCSPH multiphase flows, two main challenges we discuss in the present work are: (i) numerical instability, such as pressure instability, particle penetration at phase interfaces; and (ii) modeling the compressibility of different fluid phases. Various approaches have been proposed to tackle the two challenges, which are discussed below.

Pressure instability at multiphase interfaces is often attributed to density discontinuity. To address this issue, particular attention is paid to the treatment of density. Hu et al. [31] used the summation of density to obtain smoothed pressure field for multiphase SPH scheme, but under the assumption of uniform particle distribution. Furthermore, it does not work for free-surface problems due to the truncation of the kernel support. Another approach for density evaluation is using the continuity equation, which has been widely used and well-supported by numerical techniques. For example, Colagrossi and Landrini [32] used moving-least-squares (MLS) interpolation to frequently reinitialize density

46 at the air-water interfaces, but this introduced numerical instabilities near the
47 free surface. Hammani et al. [33] extended the δ -SPH model to multiphase
48 flow, introducing a diffusive term to improve the pressure field. Recently, Guo
49 et al. [34] proposed a new discretization scheme for the divergence of velocity
50 to ensure the stability of interfaces, indicating that the SPH operators in the
51 continuity equation at multiphase interfaces should be carefully conducted.

52 Non-uniform particle distribution is another cause of instability at interfaces.
53 A well-acknowledged numerical technique is Particle Shifting Technique (PST),
54 which shows a strong capability to maintain uniform distribution [35–39] for
55 multiphase flows problems. Specially, Oger et al. [40] adjusted particle trajec-
56 tories using an Arbitrary Lagrangian-Eulerian (ALE) formalism by applying a
57 small velocity perturbation to correct Lagrangian velocity, which is shown to be
58 accurate and stable for free-surface flows. More recently, ALE frameworks for
59 the consistent δ^+ -SPH [41] and the δ -ALE-SPH [42] model, have been proposed
60 as good alternative approaches to improve volume conservation. However, these
61 methods are primarily employed for single-phase flows. Further, when involving
62 multiphase scenarios, the PST at the multiphase interfaces needs close attention
63 to keep numerical stability and a proper implementation of PST for multiphase
64 flows is still an open problem.

65 Moreover, applying background pressure is another effective method for sta-
66 bilizing interfaces by preventing particle clumping due to negative pressure [43–
67 45]. However, the value of background pressure for phases should be carefully
68 selected, since excessive background pressure can lead to non-physical dissipa-
69 tion. In addition, Grenier et al. [46] introduced an artificial repulsive force
70 to avoid the inter-penetration phenomenon. Similarly, Monaghan and Rafiee
71 [47] proposed a repulsive force related to the ratio of the densities of the fluids.
72 Recently, Guo et al. [34] introduced an improved interface force based on the
73 work of Monaghan and Rafiee [47] to better preserve the sharpness of the in-
74 terface in violent flows. These approaches have been widely adopted by many
75 studies to maintain the sharpness of the interface [48–51]. Nevertheless, it often
76 requires choosing parameters carefully to avoid introducing excessive numerical
77 disruption. In some cases, it may lead to a gap between different fluid phases.

78 When considering the modeling of phase compressibility, the SPH method
79 primarily focuses on strongly compressible problems such as bubble merging
80 [52, 53]. In these scenarios, the compressibility of the bubble is typically modeled
81 using various Tait equations. Although the effect of air in situations like dam
82 breaking [54, 55], the flooding of a damaged cabin [56], and slamming of the
83 flat plate [49] has been explored using multiphase SPH models, the discussion
84 on the stage that an air cavity becomes closed or entrapped, is still insufficient.
85 This is mainly due to the difficulties in accurately predicting the oscillation of
86 air pressure caused by compressibility in current multiphase SPH schemes. As
87 aforementioned, it is still necessary to develop an accurate and stable multiphase
88 SPH model that is capable of high stability free from the use of background
89 pressure, repulsive force methods and considering the real compressibility of
90 phases.

91 Due to the good performance of the consistent δ^+ -SPH [41] to simulate

92 violent flows, we extend it to multiphase problems and model the compressibility
 93 of air using the real physical sound speed. With the new numerical treatment
 94 of shifting velocity at the multiphase interfaces, good stability at the interfaces
 95 is achieved without the need for additional background pressure. In the present
 96 work, six cases are simulated, including a two-phase hydrostatic test, slamming
 97 of insulation panel in the Liquefied Natural Gas (LNG) tank, water entry of
 98 wedge, two-layer liquid sloshing, and sloshing with entrapped air. The ability
 99 of present multiphase δ^+ -SPH to consider flow compressibility accurately is
 100 highlighted.

101 The paper is arranged as follows: Section 2 details the extended consistent
 102 δ^+ -SPH model for multiphase flow problems, and the test cases are presented
 103 and discussed in Section 3. The conclusion is given in Section 4. In addition,
 104 the tests of strategies for the treatment of $\delta\mathbf{u}$ -terms are discussed in [Appendix](#)
 105 [A](#).

106 2. Establishment of the multiphase consistent δ^+ -SPH model

107 2.1. Governing equation

108 In the pure Lagrangian framework, the general governing equation for weakly
 109 compressible fluid is written as:

$$\begin{cases} \frac{D\rho}{Dt} &= -\rho\nabla\cdot\mathbf{u}, \\ \rho\frac{D\mathbf{u}}{Dt} &= -\nabla p + \nabla\cdot\mathbb{V} + \rho\mathbf{g}, \\ \frac{D\mathbf{r}}{Dt} &= \mathbf{u}, \quad p = F(\rho), \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

110 where ρ , \mathbf{u} , \mathbf{r} and p represent density, velocity, position and pressure, respec-
 111 tively. \mathbf{g} represents a generic volume force. F relates the pressure field to the
 112 density. Specifically, in the present weakly compressible framework, pressure is
 113 explicitly determined using the Tait equation:

$$p = B \left[\left(\frac{\rho}{\rho_0} \right)^\gamma - 1 \right] + p_b, \quad B = \frac{\rho_0 c_0^2}{\gamma}. \quad (2)$$

114 In Eq. 2, ρ_0 represents the reference density of the fluid and γ is the adiabatic
 115 coefficient, typically set to $\gamma_w = 7.0$ for the liquid phase and $\gamma_a = 1.4$ for gas.
 116 These values are widely used in water-gas multiphase studies [57]. Here, p_b
 117 denotes the background pressure. In several previous SPH studies on multiphase
 118 flows, a uniform pressure p_b has been assumed to facilitate non-penetration at
 119 interfaces [33, 43, 44]. However, this approach has to determine the numerical
 120 value of background pressure suitably as excessive value may cause non-physical
 121 dissipation. To avoid this, $p_b = 0$ is set both for the gas and water phase and
 122 stable pressure field is obtained as well without relying on background pressure
 123 in the present scheme.

124 The sound speed, c_0 , accounts for the compressibility of different phases. For
 125 liquid phase like water, the sound speed c_{0w} is based on the weakly compressible

126 assumption, $c_{0w} \geq 10 \max(U_{\max}, \sqrt{p_{\max}/\rho_{0w}})$ where U_{\max} is the maximum
 127 expected fluid velocity, p_{\max} is the maximum expected fluid pressure, and ρ_{0w}
 128 is the reference density of water.

129 Notably, recent novel multiphase schemes allow reducing sound speeds for
 130 gas phase (e.g. [9, 33, 43]), instead of relying solely on real physical sound
 131 speeds, to improve numerical efficiency. However, in this study, to model real
 132 compressibility accurately when gas is entrapped, the numerical sound speed of
 133 the gas phase is set to the real physical sound speed, i.e., $c_{0a} = 340$ m/s.

134 2.2. Consistent δ^+ -SPH model

135 2.2.1. Discretized governing equation

136 The shifting velocity $\delta\mathbf{u}$ is straightforwardly included in the governing equa-
 137 tion reformulated into a quasi-Lagrangian framework following the studies [26,
 138 41, 42, 58, 59]; the quasi-Lagrangian derivative is given by:

$$\frac{df}{dt} = \frac{Df}{Dt} + \delta\mathbf{u} \cdot \nabla f. \quad (3)$$

139 The way to calculate the shifting velocity $\delta\mathbf{u}$ in our framework will be discussed
 140 further down, in Section 2.3. When $\delta\mathbf{u} = 0$, the framework becomes a pure
 141 Lagrangian formalism.

142 Utilizing the definition provided in Eq. 3, the consistent δ^+ -SPH multiphase
 143 model within a quasi-Lagrangian framework [41] is following:

$$\begin{cases} \frac{d\rho}{dt} &= -\rho\nabla \cdot \mathbf{u} - \rho\nabla \cdot \delta\mathbf{u} + \nabla \cdot (\rho\delta\mathbf{u}), \\ \rho \frac{d\mathbf{u}}{dt} &= -\nabla p + \nabla \cdot \mathbb{V} + \rho\mathbf{g} + \nabla \cdot (\rho\mathbf{u} \otimes \delta\mathbf{u}) - \rho\mathbf{u}\nabla \cdot (\delta\mathbf{u}), \\ \frac{d\mathbf{r}}{dt} &= \mathbf{u} + \delta\mathbf{u}, \quad p = F(\rho). \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

144 The system in Eq. 4 is identical to the single-phase consistent δ^+ -SPH model.
 145 However, aside from the treatment of the equation of state, this paper shows that
 146 the divergence terms given by $\delta\mathbf{u}$ are crucial for modeling multiphase consistent
 147 δ^+ -SPH, especially in the continuity equation. Notably, the last term $\rho\mathbf{u}\nabla \cdot (\delta\mathbf{u})$
 148 within the momentum equation of the Eq. 4 is not discretized in the following
 149 work. This simplification has also been used in the previous works [41, 59–61].
 150 As demonstrated by Sun et al. [41], including or not this term in the scheme
 151 does not seem to induce sensible differences in the final results.

152 Using the SPH approximation (details in [62, 63]), the Eq. 4 is discretized,
 153 and four key techniques are used to further improve numerical accuracy, includ-
 154 ing:

- 155 1. Using the Tensile Instability Control (TIC) [64] technique to avoid numer-
 156 ical voids.
- 157 2. Adding an acoustic damper term in the momentum equation for the in-
 158 compressible phase to achieve a smooth pressure field comparable to that
 159 in the truly incompressible hypothesis.

- 160 3. Using PST to obtain uniform particle distribution and integrating ad-
 161 vection velocity $\mathbf{u} + \delta\mathbf{u}$ into the governing equations for the multiphase
 162 δ^+ -SPH scheme.
 163 4. Introducing numerical treatments of the shifting velocity at interfaces, in-
 164 cluding fluid-solid and multiphase interfaces, to maintain a stable pressure
 165 field, as described in Section 2.4.

166 Considering these points, the present SPH scheme for multiphase flows based
 167 on the consistent δ^+ -SPH is discretized as follows:

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \frac{d\rho_i}{dt} = -\rho_i \langle \nabla \cdot \mathbf{u} \rangle_i - \rho_i \underbrace{\langle \nabla \cdot \delta\mathbf{u} \rangle_i}_{\delta\mathbf{u}\text{-term}} + \underbrace{\langle \nabla \cdot (\rho\delta\mathbf{u}) \rangle_i}_{\delta\mathbf{u}\text{-term}} + \delta h c_0 \mathcal{D}_i, \\ \rho_i \frac{d\mathbf{u}_i}{dt} = -\langle \nabla p \rangle_i + \langle \nabla \cdot \mathbb{V} \rangle_i + \rho_i \mathbf{g} + \underbrace{\langle \nabla \cdot (\rho\mathbf{u} \otimes \delta\mathbf{u}) \rangle_i}_{\delta\mathbf{u}\text{-term}} + \mathbf{F}_i^{ad}, \\ \frac{d\mathbf{r}_i}{dt} = \mathbf{u}_i + \delta\mathbf{u}_i, \quad p_i = F(\rho_i), \end{array} \right. \quad (5)$$

with

$$\mathbf{F}_i^{ad} = \begin{cases} \alpha_2 \rho_i c_0 h \langle \nabla (\nabla \cdot \mathbf{u}(\mathbf{r})) \rangle_i, & i \in \Omega_f^I \\ 0, & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases}$$

168 where the subscript j represents the neighboring particles of particle i . The
 169 diffusive coefficient $\delta = 0.1$ is used. The term \mathcal{D}_i denotes the numerical diffusive
 170 term proposed by [65], aimed at filtering out high-frequency pressure vibrations:

$$\mathcal{D}_i = \sum_{\substack{j, \\ \Omega(j)=\Omega(i)}} \psi_{ji} \frac{\mathbf{r}_{ji} \cdot \nabla_i W_{ij}}{\|\mathbf{r}_{ji}\|^2} V_j, \quad \psi_{ij} = 2(\rho_j - \rho_i) - [\langle \nabla \rho \rangle_i^L + \langle \nabla \rho \rangle_j^L] \cdot \mathbf{r}_{ji}, \quad (6)$$

171 where $\mathbf{r}_{ji} = \mathbf{r}_j - \mathbf{r}_i$, and the renormalized density gradient $\langle \nabla \rho \rangle^L$ is defined as:

$$\langle \nabla \rho \rangle_i^L = \sum_{\substack{j, \\ \Omega(j)=\Omega(i)}} (\rho_j - \rho_i) \mathbb{L}_i \nabla W_{ij} V_j, \quad \mathbb{L}_i = \left[\sum_{\substack{j, \\ \Omega(j)=\Omega(i)}} \mathbf{r}_{ji} \otimes \nabla W_{ij} V_j \right]^{-1}. \quad (7)$$

172 To prevent non-physical density diffusion between different fluids, the numerical
 173 diffusive term is applied only for particles within the same fluid set, i.e. $\Omega(j) =$
 174 $\Omega(i)$ (see Figure 1), following the work by Hammani et al. [33]; it means that
 175 the summations in Eqs. 6 and 7 all apply to particles belonging to the i th
 176 particle set $\Omega(i)$.

177 $W_{ij} = W(r_{ji}, h)$ represents the kernel function where $r_{ji} = \|\mathbf{r}_j - \mathbf{r}_i\|$, and h
 178 denotes the smoothing length. In the present work, a Gaussian kernel function
 179 [46] with compact support is employed:

$$W(r, h) = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{\pi h^2} \left[\frac{e^{-(r/h)^2} - C_0}{1 - C_1} \right], & \text{if } r \leq \epsilon h, \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}, \quad C_0 = e^{-\epsilon^2}, \quad C_1 = C_0(1 + \epsilon^2). \quad (8)$$

180 The length ϵh represents a cut-off radius, set equal to $3h$, and $h/\Delta x = 1.33$
 181 where Δx is averaged particle spacing at initialization.

182 Furthermore, the acoustic damper term \mathbf{F}_i^{ad} is incorporated for incompressible
 183 fluids (referred to as Ω_f^I) to minimize the effects associated with the weakly
 184 compressible assumption, as demonstrated in [66]. The parameter α_2 needs
 185 to be large enough to dampen acoustic waves generated during violent impact
 186 events. However, an excessively large α_2 can significantly reduce the time step
 187 (details in [66]). In multiphase scenarios, since the time step is constrained by
 188 the physical gas sound speed (see Subsection 2.2.3), which is sufficiently small,
 189 thus the parameter α_2 can be set to $\alpha_2 = 10$. This ensures smoother pressure
 190 field for the incompressible phase, closely resembling predictions under the
 191 incompressible hypothesis.

192 2.2.2. Discretized SPH differential operators

193 Now, the discretization of the differential operators on the right side of Eq.
 194 5 is introduced. These differential operators are approximated through the
 195 convolution with the kernel function. Based on the classic discretization of
 196 the pressure gradient, the technique of TIC [64] is further employed to avoid
 197 numerical voids. Specifically, when the pressure p_i of particle i located outside
 198 the free surface region Ω_A^F (see Figure 1) is negative, the classic term $p_i + p_j$
 199 is replaced by $p_j - p_i$. Conversely, particle i with positive pressure, or located in
 200 the free surface region, is still calculated in the classic form. The detection of
 201 the free surface region Ω_A^F is conducted following the procedure established by
 202 [67]. Therefore, the pressure gradient ∇p is discretized as:

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \langle \nabla p \rangle_i = \sum_j (p_j + p_i) \nabla_i W_{ij} V_j + S_i \sum_j \nabla_i W_{ij} V_j, \\ S_i = \begin{cases} 2p_i & \text{if } p_i < 0 \text{ and } i \notin \Omega_A^F, \\ 0 & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \end{array} \right. \quad (9)$$

203 The divergence of the velocity $\nabla \cdot \mathbf{u}$ and viscous stress tensor $\nabla \cdot \mathbb{V}$ are
 204 approximated through below formulas (see [30, 68] for more details):

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \langle \nabla \cdot \mathbf{u} \rangle_i = \sum_j (\mathbf{u}_j - \mathbf{u}_i) \cdot \nabla_i W_{ij} V_j, \\ \langle \nabla \cdot \mathbb{V} \rangle_i = K\mu \sum_j \pi_{ij} \nabla_i W_{ij} V_j, \\ \pi_{ij} = \frac{\mathbf{u}_{ji} \cdot \mathbf{r}_{ji}}{\|\mathbf{r}_{ji}\|^2}, \end{array} \right. \quad (10)$$

205 where μ denotes the dynamic viscosity of the fluid; parameter $K = 2(n + 2)$
 206 with n the dimension of the simulations. In cases involving violent impact flows,
 207 the coefficient $K\mu$ is directly replaced by $\alpha c_0 \rho_0 h$, α referred to as the artificial
 208 viscosity parameter, aiming to improve numerical stability. More details can
 209 be found in [65]. The coefficient α is generally recommended to vary between
 210 0 and 0.1 for violent impact problems, so a value of $\alpha = 0.1$ is adopted in the
 211 present work, unless otherwise specified.

Figure 1: Schematic diagrams with particle set definitions, where Ω represents the universe of SPH particles and $\Omega = \Omega_A \cup \Omega_B \cup \Omega_G$. Ω_A^F refers particles that belong to Ω_A and are free-surfaces particles.

212 Following [41, 42], the approximation of the terms given by shifting velocity
 213 $\delta \mathbf{u}$ (called $\delta \mathbf{u}$ -terms hereinafter) is written as:

$$\boxed{\delta \mathbf{u}\text{-terms}} \begin{cases} \langle \nabla \cdot (\delta \mathbf{u}) \rangle_i = \sum_j (\delta \mathbf{u}_j - \delta \mathbf{u}_i) \cdot \nabla_i W_{ij} V_j, \\ \langle \nabla \cdot (\rho \delta \mathbf{u}) \rangle_i = \sum_j (\rho_i \delta \mathbf{u}_i + \rho_j \delta \mathbf{u}_j) \cdot \nabla_i W_{ij} V_j, \\ \langle \nabla \cdot (\rho \mathbf{u} \otimes \delta \mathbf{u}) \rangle_i = \sum_j (\rho_i \mathbf{u}_i \otimes \delta \mathbf{u}_i + \rho_j \mathbf{u}_j \otimes \delta \mathbf{u}_j) \cdot \nabla_i W_{ij} V_j. \end{cases} \quad (11)$$

214 Specifically, the first $\delta \mathbf{u}$ -term $\nabla \cdot (\delta \mathbf{u})$ follows the same discretization strategy as
 215 the velocity divergence in Eq. 10, using $(f_j - f_i)$ differential terms where f represents
 216 a vector variable. The other two divergence operators adopt symmetric
 217 $(f_i + f_j)$ summation terms. Owing to this symmetric structure, the conservation
 218 of mass and linear momentum can be maintained [42].

219 2.2.3. Boundary implementations and time step

220 For boundary conditions, mirror ghost particle techniques theoretically provide
 221 superior accuracy and convergence, while the fixed ghost technique introduces
 222 minor numerical discrepancies in the SPH scheme. However, the practical
 223 applicability of the former is limited in engineering contexts, such as water entry
 224 simulations. Therefore, the fixed ghost particle technique is employed, as the
 225 numerical errors in the cases examined in this paper are negligible. Additionally,
 226 for potential particle penetration issues in particle-based boundaries, a strategy
 227 proposed in [69], which involves correcting the normal velocity of potentially
 228 penetrating particles near ghost particles, can be a viable alternative.

229 The discrete governing equation is updated in time using the fourth-order
 230 Rang-Kutta time integration. The time step Δt has to account for maximum
 231 acceleration $|\mathbf{a}_{\max}|$ in the flows, the sound speed, viscous diffusion. It is deter-
 232 mined based on the following conditions [66]:

$$\begin{cases} \Delta t_a = 0.25\sqrt{\frac{h}{|\mathbf{a}_{\max}|}}, \\ \Delta t_c = \text{CFL} \min\left(\frac{h}{c_{0w}}, \frac{h}{c_{0a}}, \frac{h}{c_{stab}}\right), & c_{stab} = c_{0w} \sqrt{\frac{\gamma_a \rho_{0w}}{\gamma_w \rho_{\min}^a}}, \\ \Delta t_\nu = \min\left(\frac{h}{\alpha c_{0w}}, \frac{h}{\alpha c_{0a}}\right), & \Delta t_{ad} = \text{CFL} \frac{h}{\alpha_2 c_{0w}}, \\ \Delta t \leq \min(\Delta t_c, \Delta t_\nu, \Delta t_a, \Delta t_{ad}), \end{cases} \quad (12)$$

233 where ρ_{\min}^a is the minimum density of the gas phase and CFL is the Courant-
 234 Friedrichs-Lewy number which is set to 1 in the present work. To ensure nu-
 235 merical stability, a "stable sound speed" c_{stab} is considered for the time
 236 step following the work of [52].

237 The time step Δt_ν associated with viscous effects is generally expressed as
 238 $\Delta t_\nu = 0.125\min(h^2/\nu)$ (see e.g., [70]). Since we are concerned about problems
 239 involving violent impacts, the Reynold number is generally high, and conse-
 240 quently, artificial viscosity is chosen to maintain the numerical stability. By
 241 substituting the kinematic viscosity with $\nu = \alpha h c_0 / (2n + 4)$ and the dimension
 242 $n = 2$ in the present work, the Δt_ν is written as . As indicated in Eq. 12, α is
 243 relatively small, implying that the constraint on Δt_ν is not the most restrictive.

244 The Δt_{ad} is related to the acoustic damper term, where the parameter α_2
 245 has to be large enough to achieve a smoothed pressure field similar to that solved
 246 with incompressible SPH. In singlephase problems, α_2 typically ranges from 0
 247 to 1 to ensure that Δt_{ad} remains smaller than Δt_c and Δt_a [66]. Notably, in
 248 present multiphase problems, the use of real gas sound speed $c_{0a} = 340$ m/s
 249 ensures gas physical compressibility, making Δt_c the most restrictive factor. As
 250 a result, the parameter α_2 can be as high as 10, further achieving a smoothed
 251 pressure field. In this way, a weakly compressible phase, like water, behaves
 252 more like an incompressible one due to the high acoustic damping, and the
 253 compressibility of the compressible phase, like gas, can also be well modeled
 254 with the physical sound speed.

255 2.3. Determination of the shifting velocity $\delta \mathbf{u}$ at different regions of the flow

256 In the δ^+ -SPH scheme [71], the shifting velocity is simply used to regu-
 257 larize the particle distribution, but not taken into account in the continuity
 258 and momentum equations. In contrast, in the present multiphase scheme, it
 259 is integrated into the governing equations rather than applied as an external
 260 displacement correction. To further clarify the effect of the two approaches, a
 261 comparison of the numerical results between these two approaches will be pro-
 262 vided in Subsection 3.2. The formula for shifting velocity is defined according
 263 to the work [41] as follows:

$$\delta \bar{\mathbf{u}}_i = -2h\text{Mac}_0 \sum_j \nabla_i W_{ij} V_j, \quad (13)$$

264 where Ma denotes the Mach number which is U_{\max}/c_0 .

265 However, the expression above has to be modified for particles in some special
 266 regions including free surface region Ω_A^F and solid walls Ω_G (see Figure 1). For
 267 free surface region, only the tangential component of $\delta\bar{\mathbf{u}}_i$ is considered, similar
 268 to the work of Sun et al. [72]. In this study, we introduce a novel treatment
 269 for $\delta\mathbf{u}$ -terms at the fluid-solid interface, which will be discussed in the following
 270 subsection. This treatment allows us to set the shifting velocity $\delta\mathbf{u}$ of ghost
 271 particles to zero, differing from previous works that considered $\delta\mathbf{u}$ for ghost
 272 particles (see e.g., [40]). This simplification avoids complex treatment on the
 273 ghost particles and further enhances computational efficiency. Furthermore, the
 274 stability of the implementation of the PST at the fluid-solid interface will be
 275 discussed and validation in Section 3. Therefore, the shifting velocity $\delta\bar{\mathbf{u}}_i$ is
 276 modified:

$$\delta\bar{\mathbf{u}}_i = \begin{cases} 0, & \text{if } i \in \Omega_G, \\ (\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{n}_i \otimes \mathbf{n}_i) \delta\bar{\mathbf{u}}_i, & \text{if } i \in \Omega_A^F, \\ \delta\bar{\mathbf{u}}_i, & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases} \quad (14)$$

277 where \mathbf{I} denotes an identity matrix, and \mathbf{n}_i represents the normal vector along
 278 the free surface of the i th particle. Further details on the surface identification
 279 and normal vector computation can be found in [67]. To further improve the
 280 numerical stability, a limit is imposed on the shifting term, so velocity deviation
 281 $\delta\mathbf{u}$ is finally expressed as:

$$\delta\mathbf{u}_i = \begin{cases} \delta\bar{\mathbf{u}}_i, & \text{if } \|\delta\bar{\mathbf{u}}_i\| < 0.5U_{\max} \text{ or } i \in \Omega_A^F \vee \Omega_G \\ 0.5U_{\max} \frac{\delta\bar{\mathbf{u}}_i}{\|\delta\bar{\mathbf{u}}_i\|}, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (15)$$

282 2.4. Extension of the consistent δ^+ -SPH model for multiphase flows: new treat- 283 ments of $\delta\mathbf{u}$ -terms

284 In a multiphase system, particles at interfaces (i.e. fluid-solid and multi-
 285 fluid interfaces) often interact with neighboring particles that belong to differ-
 286 ent phases. Proper handling of these interactions is essential for maintaining
 287 stability at multiphase interfaces. Hence, for extending consistent δ^+ -SPH to
 288 multiphase flows, the treatment of $\delta\mathbf{u}$ -terms is a key challenge. To account for
 289 these interactions, we introduce the parameters ε , φ , and κ to adjust the con-
 290 tribution of neighboring particles to the $\delta\mathbf{u}$ -terms. We then rewrite Eq. 11 as
 291 follows:

$$\boxed{\delta\mathbf{u}\text{-terms}} \begin{cases} \langle \nabla \cdot (\delta\mathbf{u}) \rangle_i = \sum_j (\varepsilon_{ij} \delta\mathbf{u}_j - \varepsilon_{ii} \delta\mathbf{u}_i) \cdot \nabla_i W_{ij} V_j \\ \langle \nabla \cdot (\rho \delta\mathbf{u}) \rangle_i = \sum_j (\varphi_{ij} \rho_j \delta\mathbf{u}_j + \varphi_{ii} \rho_i \delta\mathbf{u}_i) \cdot \nabla_i W_{ij} V_j \\ \langle \nabla \cdot (\rho \mathbf{u} \otimes \delta\mathbf{u}) \rangle_i = \sum_j \kappa_{ij} (\rho_i \mathbf{u}_i \otimes \delta\mathbf{u}_i + \rho_j \mathbf{u}_j \otimes \delta\mathbf{u}_j) \cdot \nabla_i W_{ij} V_j. \end{cases} \quad (16)$$

292 Here, the subscripts ii and ij of the parameters ε , φ , and κ represent contri-
 293 butions from the particle i itself and the neighboring particle j , respectively.

294 The adoptions of ε for the discretization of $\nabla \cdot (\delta \mathbf{u})_i$, φ for the discretization of
 295 $\nabla \cdot (\rho \delta \mathbf{u})_i$ in the continuity equation; and κ for the discretization of $\nabla \cdot (\rho \mathbf{u} \otimes \delta \mathbf{u})_i$
 296 in the momentum equation are introduced in the following subsections.

297 2.4.1. Numerical treatments of the $\delta \mathbf{u}$ -term in the momentum equation

298 The $\delta \mathbf{u}$ -term in the momentum equation is computed only when the particles
 299 i and j both belong to the same fluid phase. This means that the computing
 300 domain of the term $\nabla \cdot (\rho \mathbf{u} \otimes \delta \mathbf{u})$ is restricted to a specific fluid phase. Conse-
 301 quently, the parameter κ_{ij} is selected as follows:

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \langle \nabla \cdot (\rho \mathbf{u} \otimes \delta \mathbf{u}) \rangle_i = \sum_j \kappa_{ij} (\rho_i \mathbf{u}_i \otimes \delta \mathbf{u}_i + \rho_j \mathbf{u}_j \otimes \delta \mathbf{u}_j) \cdot \nabla_i W_{ij} V_j \\ \kappa_{ij} = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } \Omega(i) = \Omega(j), \\ 0, & \text{if } \Omega(i) \neq \Omega(j). \end{cases} \end{array} \right. \quad (17)$$

302 Thanks to the symmetric structure of $\langle \nabla \cdot (\rho \mathbf{u} \otimes \delta \mathbf{u}) \rangle_i$ and the discretization
 303 that it only considers the same phase, this term remains unchanged when swap-
 304 ping the indexes i and j . Consequently, this term in the momentum equation
 305 does not affect the overall linear momentum conservation of the system.

306 2.4.2. Numerical treatments of the $\delta \mathbf{u}$ -terms in the continuity equation

307 Effective management of the $\delta \mathbf{u}$ -terms within the continuity equation is es-
 308 sential to ensure the stability and accuracy of the pressure field. Furthermore,
 309 within the multiphase scheme, the discontinuity of density at multiphase inter-
 310 faces increases the complexity of this issue. So, in the present subsection, we
 311 focus on the discretization of the $\delta \mathbf{u}$ -terms (Eq. 16) in the continuity equation.
 312 The strategies for handing $\delta \mathbf{u}$ -terms at fluid-solid and multi-fluid interfaces are
 313 discussed separately, as detailed below:

314 • Strategy for $\delta \mathbf{u}$ -terms applied at the fluid-solid interface

315 As described in Eq. 14, the shifting velocity $\delta \mathbf{u}$ for the ghost particles in
 316 the solid wall is zero. In terms of the first $\delta \mathbf{u}$ -term $\nabla \cdot (\delta \mathbf{u})$ in the continuity
 317 equation, the parameter ε is set to $\varepsilon_{ii} = \varepsilon_{ij} = 1$ straightforwardly. However, in
 318 terms of the second $\delta \mathbf{u}$ -term $\nabla \cdot (\rho \delta \mathbf{u})$, the numerical instability in the pressure
 319 field occurs if the density of solid particles is directly involved since the density
 320 of the ghost particles is spurious.

321 To avoid such instability, a strategy is employed which restricts the compu-
 322 tation of $\nabla \cdot (\rho \delta \mathbf{u})$ only between particle pairs ($i \leftrightarrow j$) of the same fluid-phase.
 323 In other words, for a fluid particle, the solid wall particle has no influence on
 324 the calculation of the term $\nabla \cdot (\rho \delta \mathbf{u})$. This is achieved by setting $\varphi_{ii} = \varphi_{ij} = 0$
 325 when particle i and j are from different particle sets, that is, when $\Omega(i) \neq \Omega(j)$
 326 at the fluid-solid interface. Accordingly, the strategy for selecting ε and φ at

327 the fluid-solid interface is summarized as follows:

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \langle \nabla \cdot (\delta \mathbf{u}) \rangle_i = \sum_j (\varepsilon_{ij} \delta \mathbf{u}_j - \varepsilon_{ii} \delta \mathbf{u}_i) \cdot \nabla_i W_{ij} V_j \\ \langle \nabla \cdot (\rho \delta \mathbf{u}) \rangle_i = \sum_j (\varphi_{ij} \rho_j \delta \mathbf{u}_j + \varphi_{ii} \rho_i \delta \mathbf{u}_i) \cdot \nabla_i W_{ij} V_j \\ \varepsilon_{ii} = 1, \quad \varepsilon_{ij} = 1 \\ \varphi_{ii} = \varphi_{ij} = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } \Omega(i) = \Omega(j), \\ 0, & \text{if } \Omega(i) \neq \Omega(j). \end{cases} \end{array} \right. \quad (18)$$

328 In this strategy, the density of solid wall particles is excluded from the ap-
 329 proximation of $\nabla \cdot (\rho \delta \mathbf{u})$, ensuring that the influence of solid particles does not
 330 introduce spurious effects in the pressure field.

331 **• Strategy for $\delta \mathbf{u}$ -terms applied at the multi-fluid interface**

332 We propose an alternative strategy for discretizing the $\delta \mathbf{u}$ -terms in the con-
 333 tinuity equation at the multi-fluid interface, and the two $\delta \mathbf{u}$ -terms are treated
 334 in the same manner. In this strategy, the contribution of particle i across its
 335 entire support domain is always considered, while the influence of neighboring
 336 particles from other phases is ignored. To implement this strategy, the following
 337 modification is introduced:

338 For the contribution from particle i itself, both $\varepsilon_{ii} = 1$ and $\varphi_{ii} = 1$ are
 339 adopted, regardless the neighboring particle j belongs to which kind of particle
 340 sets. For the contribution of particle j , when particle i interacts with neigh-
 341 boring particle j from a different particle set, it is ignored by setting $\varepsilon_{ij} = 0$
 342 and $\varphi_{ij} = 0$. Furthermore, this strategy also avoids directly using the density
 343 of other phases in computing $\nabla \cdot (\rho \delta \mathbf{u})$ in the continuity equation. Finally,
 344 the strategy for selecting ε and φ at the multi-fluid interface is summarized as
 345 follows:

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \langle \nabla \cdot (\delta \mathbf{u}) \rangle_i = \sum_j (\varepsilon_{ij} \delta \mathbf{u}_j - \varepsilon_{ii} \delta \mathbf{u}_i) \cdot \nabla_i W_{ij} V_j \\ \langle \nabla \cdot (\rho \delta \mathbf{u}) \rangle_i = \sum_j (\varphi_{ij} \rho_j \delta \mathbf{u}_j + \varphi_{ii} \rho_i \delta \mathbf{u}_i) \cdot \nabla_i W_{ij} V_j \\ \varepsilon_{ii} = 1, \quad \varepsilon_{ij} = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } \Omega(i) = \Omega(j), \\ 0, & \text{if } \Omega(i) \neq \Omega(j). \end{cases} \\ \varphi_{ii} = 1, \quad \varphi_{ij} = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } \Omega(i) = \Omega(j), \\ 0, & \text{if } \Omega(i) \neq \Omega(j). \end{cases} \end{array} \right. \quad (19)$$

346 *2.5. Final form of the discrete equations of multiphase consistent δ^+ SPH*

347 As discussed previously, the consistent δ^+ -SPH model extended for multi-
 348 phase flows requires careful treatment of terms involving the shifting velocity
 349 $\delta \mathbf{u}$, particularly at fluid-solid and multi-fluid interfaces. In order to provide a
 350 clear illustration of the present multiphase δ^+ -SPH model, we suppose a fluid
 351 particle $i \in \Omega_A$; the neighboring particle j of it can belong to the same fluid
 352 phase Ω_A , different fluid phases Ω_B , or the solid phase Ω_G , see Figure 1.

353 Table 1 details the contributions of neighboring particles from different particle
354 sets to the discretization of $\delta\mathbf{u}$ -terms. By identifying the set to which each
355 neighboring particle belongs, the parameters ε , φ , and κ are determined. Based
356 on Table 1, the $\delta\mathbf{u}$ -terms of particle i can be clearly computed at multi-fluid and
357 fluid-solid interfaces, even for special cases where the fluid particle i is neigh-
358 boring solid wall particles, particles from different fluid sets and particles from
359 the same set within its support domain simultaneously.

Table 1: Final form of the multiphase δ^+ -SPH model with new treatments of the $\delta\mathbf{u}$ -terms. Supposing a fluid particle i belongs to particle set Ω_A , the neighboring particle j of fluid particle i thus can belong to particle sets Ω_A , Ω_B , or Ω_G .

Continuity equation	$\frac{d\rho_i}{dt} = -\rho_i\langle\nabla\cdot\mathbf{u}\rangle_i - \rho_i\underbrace{\langle\nabla\cdot\delta\mathbf{u}\rangle_i}_{\delta\mathbf{u}\text{-term}} + \underbrace{\langle\nabla\cdot(\rho\delta\mathbf{u})\rangle_i}_{\delta\mathbf{u}\text{-term}} + \delta hc_0\mathcal{D}_i$		
Momentum equation	$\rho_i\frac{d\mathbf{u}_i}{dt} = -\langle\nabla p\rangle_i + \langle\nabla\cdot\nabla\rangle_i + \rho_i\mathbf{g} + \underbrace{\langle\nabla\cdot(\rho\mathbf{u}\otimes\delta\mathbf{u})\rangle_i}_{\delta\mathbf{u}\text{-term}} + \mathbf{F}_i^{ad}$		
Discretization of $\delta\mathbf{u}$ -terms	$\begin{cases} \langle\nabla\cdot(\delta\mathbf{u})\rangle_i = \sum_j (\varepsilon_{ij}\delta\mathbf{u}_j - \varepsilon_{ii}\delta\mathbf{u}_i) \cdot \nabla_i W_{ij} V_j \\ \langle\nabla\cdot(\rho\delta\mathbf{u})\rangle_i = \sum_j (\varphi_{ij}\rho_j\delta\mathbf{u}_j + \varphi_{ii}\rho_i\delta\mathbf{u}_i) \cdot \nabla_i W_{ij} V_j \\ \langle\nabla\cdot(\rho\mathbf{u}\otimes\delta\mathbf{u})\rangle_i = \sum_j \kappa_{ij} (\rho_i\mathbf{u}_i \otimes \delta\mathbf{u}_i + \rho_j\mathbf{u}_j \otimes \delta\mathbf{u}_j) \cdot \nabla_i W_{ij} V_j \end{cases}$		
If $i \in \Omega_A$, set of neighboring particle j	If $j \in \Omega_A$	If $j \in \Omega_B$	If $j \in \Omega_G$
Parameters of $\delta\mathbf{u}$ -terms	$\begin{cases} \varepsilon_{ii} = \varepsilon_{ij} = 1 \\ \varphi_{ii} = \varphi_{ij} = 1 \\ \kappa_{ij} = 1 \end{cases}$	$\begin{cases} \varepsilon_{ii} = 1, \quad \varepsilon_{ij} = 0, \\ \varphi_{ii} = 1, \quad \varphi_{ij} = 0, \\ \kappa_{ij} = 0 \end{cases}$	$\begin{cases} \varepsilon_{ii} = 1, \quad \varepsilon_{ij} = 1, \\ \varphi_{ii} = 0, \quad \varphi_{ij} = 0, \\ \kappa_{ij} = 0 \end{cases}$

360 It should be noted that in this work the particle mass is assumed to be
361 constant. Consequently, mass conservation can be effectively maintained in
362 these strategies. Due to the careful treatment of the $\delta\mathbf{u}$ -terms at interfaces,
363 the present δ^+ SPH model exhibits stable behavior without the need for addi-
364 tional numerical techniques, such as background pressure, to handle interface
365 instability. Among the different strategies we have tried (see more details in the
366 [Appendix A](#).), the strategies for discretization of $\delta\mathbf{u}$ -terms proposed in subsec-
367 tion 2.4 are the most stable for the treatment of multiphase interfaces. Various
368 test cases are presented to validate the performance of the current multiphase
369 SPH model in terms of stability, convergence and accuracy in the following sec-
370 tion. Further theoretical studies on the strategies for treating the $\delta\mathbf{u}$ -terms at
371 multiphase interfaces will be explored in future work.

372 3. SPH results and discussions

373 The consistent δ^+ -SPH model extended for multiphase flows in the present
374 work is validated through six cases: two-phase hydrostatic test, multiphase dam
375 breaking, slamming of LNG tank insulation panels, wedge water entry, two-layer
376 liquid sloshing, and sloshing with entrapped air pockets. These comprehensive
377 cases also include accurately probing and validating air pressure and evaluating
378 the capability of handling free surface in the last two cases.

Figure 2: The time history of the ratio between total kinetic energy E_k and potential energy E_p of the air phase (left) and the water phase (right) simulated with three particle resolutions, and compared with the result of Hammani et al. [33].

Figure 3: The pressure field of two-phase hydrostatic at instant $t (g/H_w)^{1/2} = 40$ (left), and the pressure distribution along the vertical centerline of the rectangular tank, compared with analytic trend (right). The numerical error, defined as $(p^{\text{SPH}} - p^{\text{Analytic}})/(\rho g H_w)$ is also plotted on the right side. The ρ here is taken as water density $\rho = 1000 \text{ kg/m}^3$.

379 *3.1. Two-phase hydrostatic test*

380 Firstly, to assess the stability and robustness of the current multiphase SPH
 381 model, a two-phase hydrostatic scenario is simulated in a rectangular tank in
 382 this subsection. The rectangular tank is of length H_w and height $2H_w$ with the
 383 upper half filled with air and the lower half filled with water. The density of
 384 the water and air phase is set as 1000 kg/m^3 and 1 kg/m^3 , respectively.

385 In this case, three particle resolutions $H_w/\Delta x = 50$, $H_w/\Delta x = 100$, and
 386 $H_w/\Delta x = 200$ are adopted, respectively. With the particle resolution increas-
 387 ing, the energy fluctuation at initial time due to the initial Cartesian distribution
 388 can effectively decrease. This issue has been discussed in [73], where a particle
 389 packing algorithm was proposed to reduce spurious initialization effects and im-
 390 prove numerical stability. As shown in Figure 2, the disturbing kinetic energy of
 391 the two phases decreases rapidly and converges close to zero with particle res-
 392 olution $H_w/\Delta x = 200$, indicating that the present multiphase δ^+ -SPH model
 393 achieves good convergence with $H_w/\Delta x = 200$ and this particle resolution is
 394 chosen to discuss following. Additionally, compared to the results from [33]
 395 simulated with the multiphase δ -SPH model, the disturbing kinetic energy of
 396 the two phases in the present scheme converges more quickly due to the effect
 397 of PST. However, the use of PST can contribute some kinetic energy, as long as
 398 the particle distribution is not uniform during the simulation. As a result, the
 399 settled energy is slightly higher than the result simulated by Hammami et al.
 400 [33]. Furthermore, the adoption of background pressure in the work of Ham-
 401 mani et al. [33] can also lead to some numerical dissipation [64], contributing
 402 to a lower kinetic energy. However, the energy ratio of 10^{-8} with particle res-
 403 olution $H_w/\Delta x = 200$ is sufficiently low to confirm the stability of the present
 404 multiphase scheme.

405 At $t (g/H_w)^{1/2} = 40$, as illustrated on the left side of Figure 3, the pressure
 406 distribution of water and gas phases remains stable. On the right side of Figure
 407 3, the pressure distribution along the centerline of the tank is compared with
 408 the analytical trend plotted along the bottom axis, and the numerical error
 409 calculated by $(p^{\text{SPH}} - p^{\text{Analytic}})/(\rho g H_w)$ is plotted along the top axis. As one
 410 can observe, the pressure gradient near the water-air interface is accurately
 411 captured, with the numerical error as low as -0.8% , demonstrating that the
 412 present model maintains stable behavior at the multi-fluid interface over long-
 413 term simulations as well.

414 Furthermore, as shown in Figure 4, the particles are uniformly distributed
 415 and no interpenetration occurs at the water-air interface during the extended
 416 simulation period without the need of background pressure.

417 *3.2. Dam-break flows impacting a solid wall*

418 It is well-known that dam breaking involves surface breaking and violent
 419 impact phenomena, being a classic benchmark (see [32, 45] as examples) in the
 420 SPH community to validate the accuracy and stability of SPH models. In this
 421 Subsection, water-air phase dam breaking impacting a solid wall simulated with

Figure 4: The particle distribution of two-phase hydrostatic at instant $t(g/H_w)^{1/2} = 40$.

Figure 5: The dam breaking scenario involves a water body with a height of H and a width of $2H$. The remaining region is filled with the air phase.

422 the δ^+ -SPH model proposed by Sun et al. [71] and the present multiphase δ^+ -
 423 SPH model is discussed. Figure 5 shows the geometrical configuration and the
 424 initial pressure distribution of the water phase can be seen in [74]. The height
 425 of the water body is $H = 0.6$ m and the width $2H = 1.2$ m. Additionally, the
 426 experimental sensors, each with a diameter of $d = 90$ mm, are located $y_1 = 160$
 427 mm and $y_2 = 584$ mm away from the bottom wall, respectively. Accordingly,
 428 the numerical probes p_1 and p_2 , are placed at the bottom of the experimental
 429 sensors at $y_1 = 115$ mm and $y_2 = 539$ mm, respectively.

430 Figure 6 depicts the pressure fields and water shapes simulated by the δ^+ -
 431 SPH model with simple particle shifting [71] and the present multiphase δ^+ -SPH
 432 model at several instants. Observing the shape of water at $t = 1.37$ s, the water
 433 impacts the downstream wall and climbs along the solid wall. Furthermore,
 434 more water particles splash into the air region, as observed at $t = 1.52$ s. These
 435 evolutions of impact flows can be accurately captured by the two multiphase
 436 SPH models. According to the experimental setup, water and outside air connected
 437 to the atmosphere are essentially incompressible, whereas the entrapped

Figure 6: The results of pressure field simulated with the present multiphase δ^+ -SPH model(left column) and δ^+ -SPH proposed by Sun et al. [71] (right column) for multiphase flows.

438 air pocket undergoes compression and expansion. However, the results show a
 439 noticeable discrepancy that the air pressure simulated by the δ^+ -SPH model
 440 [71] increases significantly during the impact state. This is because in the δ^+ -
 441 SPH model proposed by Sun et al. [71], the shifting velocity is simply used
 442 to regularize the particle distribution, but not considered in the discrete form
 443 of the governing equations, which may lead to the non-conservation of volume
 444 and therefore leads to the increase of the background pressure (green curve) in
 445 Figure 7. To alleviate the above issue, the present work focuses on treating the
 446 $\delta\mathbf{u}$ -terms at the multiphase interfaces, the results of which, are well illustrated
 447 by the pressure contour shown on the left side of Figure 6 and the evolution of
 448 pressure (red curve) predicted in Figure 7.

449 Comparisons of the pressure of the two sensors between the experimental
 450 [75] and numerical results are shown in Figure 7. The results of the SPH simu-
 451 lation are in good agreement with the experimental data [75] before water
 452 overturning, especially at the sensor p_2 . As shown in Figure 6 at $t = 1.52$ s,

Figure 7: The evolution of pressure monitored at p_1 (top) and p_2 (bottom), simulating by δ^+ -SPH model with simple particle shifting [71] and the present multiphase δ^+ -SPH model compared with experimental data [75].

453 air entrainment occurs near the right wall, leading to compression and expansion
 454 of the entrapped air. Consequently, the water near the pressure sensor p_1
 455 experiences excitation, and results in pressure oscillations that can be observed
 456 in Figure 7. However, these behaviors are not visible with the experimental
 457 sensors due to 3D effects.

458 Furthermore, we compare the time history of pressure at the point p_1 be-
 459 tween single- and multiphase δ -SPH results of Antuono et al. [76] in Figure
 460 8 with the 2D SPH simulations. It is observed that the aforementioned pres-
 461 sure oscillations are captured in multiphase simulations, while the single-phase
 462 simulation fails due to the lack of consideration of the air phase. Notably, the
 463 pressure oscillations are more periodic and less noisy when simulated with the
 464 present multiphase δ^+ -SPH. The accuracy of the air phase pressure obtained by
 465 the present multiphase δ^+ SPH will be qualitatively validated in the following
 466 subsections.

467 As mentioned earlier, in the present multiphase scheme, the interface sta-
 468 bility achieved is free from background pressure and repulsive force methods.
 469 Instead, PST helps to maintain the stability of interfaces. To better understand
 470 the effects of artificial viscosity and PST, we also simulate the dam-breaking
 471 case with artificial viscosity parameter $\alpha = 0.02$. As seen in Figure 9, the pres-
 472 sure field is also smoothed and particle distribution is uniform, despite some
 473 minor splashing observed at $t = 1.63$ s. Particularly, at longer times, such as

Figure 8: Comparison of the evolution of pressure monitored at p_1 between single- and multiphase δ -SPH given by Antuono et al. [76] and the present multiphase δ^+ -SPH model.

474 $t = 3.2$ s, the physical separation between the gas and water particles is nat-
 475 urally achieved, with the gas particles as light phase staying on top and the
 476 water particles as dense phase remaining below. This suggests that artificial
 477 viscosity is not the primary factor in ensuring interface stability. For the case
 478 with $\alpha = 0.1$, Figure 10 shows that the particle distribution does not exhibit
 479 penetration into the phase interface. Importantly, even in cases of air entrapped
 480 and large interface deformation, the present SPH model simulated with either
 481 $\alpha = 0.1$ or $\alpha = 0.02$, effectively preserves a smooth interface, free from non-
 482 physical gaps. However, less splashing is observed with $\alpha = 0.1$. Therefore, to
 483 obtain a clearer interface for violent impact problems, $\alpha = 0.1$ is selected in
 484 the present work. Furthermore, the numerical results without particle splashing
 485 are similar between the two values of α , which will be further discussed in
 486 Subsection 3.5.

487 Moreover, in the present work, we highlight that the proper implementa-
 488 tion of the PST is the key factor in stabilizing the interfaces rather than rely-
 489 ing on the use of $\alpha = 0.1$. As demonstrated in the Appendix A, improper
 490 handling of the PST at multiphase interfaces can lead to noise pressure and
 491 inter-penetration, potentially causing simulation failure despite using $\alpha = 0.1$.
 492 Thanks to the proper strategies for the implementation of the PST in Section
 493 2.4, interpenetration is successfully avoided.

494 3.3. Slamming of LNG tank insulation panel

495 In this subsection, in order to validate the capability of the present multi-
 496 phase SPH model to handle fluid-solid interaction problems, and following the
 497 experiment of Marrone et al. [77], a complex problem of LNG tank insulation
 498 panel slamming is studied, where the effect of air cushion should not be ne-
 499 glected. So in this case, the ability of the present multiphase scheme to model
 500 air compressibility can be further validated. It is notable that in this case, the
 501 air is compressed into a very small volume and with a high-peak pressure, which
 502 may cause nonphysical interface penetration. A sharpness force is applied in the
 503 momentum equation in Eq. 4. This force helps preserve interface clarity in this
 504 particular case, while in other scenarios studied in this work, interface stability

Figure 9: The pressure field (left) and particle distribution (right) simulated with artificial viscosity parameter $\alpha = 0.02$.

Figure 10: Particle distribution of dam breaking problem simulated by present consistent multiphase δ^+ -SPH model with $\alpha = 0.1$. Zoom-in view of the flow region near the interface with large deformation.

Figure 11: The numerical setup and diagram of 2D profile of the LNG tank insulation panel. Its length is $L = 0.64$ m and its mass is $M_s = 1500$ kg. Four pressure monitor points 37, 40, 47, 49 are placed on the panel.

505 is maintained without the need for the sharpness force. The interface sharpness
 506 force $F_i^{sharpness}$ [46] added to the momentum equation is written as

$$F_i^{sharpness} = -\chi \sum_{\substack{j \notin \Omega_G, \\ \Omega(j) \neq \Omega(i)}} (\|p_i\| + \|p_j\|) \cdot \nabla_i W_{ij} V_j, \quad (20)$$

507 where $\chi = 0.08$ is adopted.

508 The insulation panel with a mass of $M_s = 1500$ kg falls with an impact
 509 velocity of $U_0 = 6.0$ m/s. The particle resolution is $L/\Delta x = 320$. The initial
 510 configuration and geometric characteristics of the panel are illustrated in Figure
 511 11. The initial configuration of the LNG profile is set at a height of 0.02 m above
 512 the free surface, in order to account for the air effect. The sound speed of the
 513 water is set at a value of $c_{0w} = 212$ m/s.

514 After 0.0036 s, the left dent of LNG tank insulation panel reaches water
 515 free surface. This moment is denoted as $t = -0.0036$ s, so the time when
 516 the panel touches the free surface is defined as $t = 0$ s. Figure 12 illustrates
 517 the evolution of pressure at four monitoring points designated as 37, 40, 47,
 518 and 49, respectively. The pressure loads of the four points predicted by the
 519 present multiphase SPH generally agree with the experimental data given in
 520 [77]. Compared to the numerical results obtained by Marrone et al. [77] using
 521 the Riemann-ALE SPH scheme, the pressure peaks in this study are larger and
 522 closer to the experimental data, particularly at points 40 and 47, where the
 523 pressure peaks are strongly associated with air bubble oscillations. This can be
 524 attributed to the accurate modeling of air compressibility using physical sound
 525 speed in the present multiphase scheme.

526 Typical instants of air entrapped are given in Figure 13. As the panel falls,
 527 air is entrapped and compressed seeing at instants $t = 0.009$ s and $t = 0.011$
 528 s. Subsequently, the pressure of air rises and peaks between $t = 0.009$ s and

Figure 12: The evolution of pressure compared with experimental data and SPH results of Marrone et al. [77] probed at monitor points 37, 40, 47, 49.

529 $t = 0.014$ s, which can also be observed in the pressure history at points 40 and
530 47 in Figure 12. As air escapes from the right dent at $t = 0.014$ s, the air bubble
531 expands and the pressure decreases.

532 3.4. The whole process of wedge water entry

533 According to the experiment of Wang et al. [78], the whole process of water
534 entry is simulated with particular attention to the state of cavity closure in this
535 subsection. A wedge with mass $M_s = 32.3$ kg penetrating water surface with
536 an impact velocity $U_0 = 0.92$ m/s and the Froude number $F_n = U_0\sqrt{gD} = 0.72$
537 is studied. The initial setup and shape parameters of the wedge are shown in
538 Figure 14.

539 Firstly, the convergence of particle spacing is conducted. Three particle
540 resolutions related to the width of the wedge D respectively are $D/\Delta x = 25$,
541 $D/\Delta x = 50$ and $D/\Delta x = 100$. As plotted in Figure 15, the evolution of the
542 pressure probed at $p1$ converges when the particle resolution reaches $D/\Delta x = 50$
543 and $D/\Delta x = 100$. Therefore, the particle resolution $D/\Delta x = 100$ is employed
544 in the following discussion in this subsection.

545 The simulation results of the whole process of wedge water entry including
546 the pressure probed on the impact side $p1$ and the upper wedge surface $p2$ are
547 verified with the experimental results shown in Figure 16. The pressure value
548 probed at $p1$ is shown on the left axis and $p2$ on the right axis of the graph. As
549 can be seen, the pressure at $p1$ reaches a peak value rapidly and then develops
550 into a steady value before the cavity pinch-off, which shows good agreement
551 with experimental data. Regarding the pressure at $p2$, without entrained air
552 before cavity pinch-off, the air pressure remains stable and close to 0.

553 Moreover, Figure 17 compares the flow simulated by the present multiphase
554 SPH model and obtained by experiment at the same instants before the cavity
555 pinch-off. Good agreement is obtained between them, demonstrating the ability
556 of the present scheme.

557 The pressure oscillation in the cavity dominates the water entry dynamics
558 after cavity pinch-off. As depicted in Figure 16, the oscillation period of the
559 pressure evolutions ($p1$ and $p2$) between the present SPH simulation and ex-
560 periment [78] is similar, except for the time at pinch-off the open cavity. This
561 slight discrepancy may be attributed to the three-dimensional flow effects. The
562 pressure field just after the cavity pitch-off is depicted in Figure 18. At time
563 $t = 0.347$ s, one can observe when the open cavity is about to close, the pres-
564 sure of the certain points near the pinch-off position is higher than the ambient
565 pressure. At $t = 0.352$ s, a pressure shock wave is generated at the pinch-off
566 position, compressing the cavity with high-pressure water and leading to an in-
567 crease the pressure of cavity. Importantly, the large-scale pressure wave at the
568 impact position, as discussed in [51, 66], is effectively mitigated due to the in-
569 clusion of an acoustic damper in the present scheme. As the cavity compresses,
570 the pressure peak reaches the first maximum pressure peak higher than ambi-
571 ent water pressure, causing the cavity to expand and rapidly release pressure, as
572 observed at $t = 0.357$ s and $t = 0.366$ s. Subsequently, as the cavity compresses
573 again, the pressure increases, and the second pressure peak decreases as the

Figure 13: The pressure field (left) and particle distribution (right) at instants when air is entrapped.

Figure 14: The diagram of the initial numerical setup. The wedge is simplified into an isosceles triangle structure with a dead-rise angle $\phi = 30^\circ$. Its length is $D = 0.166$ m and its mass is $M_s = 32.3$ kg. Two pressure monitors placed at $p1$ and $p2$ on the wedge are used to probe the pressure at the water surface and the air surface, respectively.

Figure 15: The evolution of pressure probed Figure 16: The verification of the pressure at the $p1$ simulated with particle resolutions $D/\Delta x = 25$, $D/\Delta x = 50$ and $D/\Delta x = 100$. experiment data. [78]

Figure 17: Comparisons between SPH results and experimental snapshots [78] during the water entry stage before the pinching-off of the cavity.

574 result of energy dissipation shown in Figure 16 and $t = 0.382$ s in Figure 18.
 575 The snapshots of the third pressure oscillation are also depicted in the last row
 576 of Figure 18.

577 Based on the above discussion, the present multiphase model can effectively
 578 simulate fluid-solid interaction and cavity oscillation dynamics.

579 3.5. Two-layer liquid sloshing

580 The sloshing of two-layer case from Xue et al. [79] is simulated to validate the
 581 accuracy of the present multiphase δ^+ -SPH model to handle free-surface prob-
 582 lems. The setup is illustrated in Figure 19. Consistent with the experimental
 583 setup, a rectangular tank with a length of $L_s = 0.57$ m is utilized. Its motion is
 584 governed by a single-degree-of-freedom motion described as $x(t) = -A(\cos \omega t)$,
 585 where $A = 0.01$ m and $\omega = 7.57$ rad/s. The upper liquid layer is diesel oil with
 586 a density of $\rho = 846$ kg/m³ and thickness $h_1 = 0.05$ m, while the lower layer
 587 is water with a density of $\rho = 1000$ kg/m³ and thickness $h_2 = 0.1$ m. Two
 588 gauges (referred to as WG2 and WG1 in Figure 19) are placed, respectively, at
 589 distances of 10 cm from the left and right walls to monitor the interfacial wave
 590 evaluation η .

591 The SPH results for interface wave elevation η simulated with three particle
 592 resolutions are shown in Figure 20. It can be observed that the cycle period
 593 and magnitudes of the SPH results with particle resolutions $h_1/\Delta x = 20$ and
 594 $h_1/\Delta x = 40$ are quite similar. Therefore, the results with a particle resolution
 595 of $h_1/\Delta x = 40$ show convergence, and this resolution is used for further dis-
 596 cussion in this subsection. Additionally, the present SPH results for interface
 597 wave elevation η are verified against the experimental data shown in Figure 21,
 598 demonstrating good agreement.

599 Figure 22 presents a comparison between the present SPH results and the
 600 experimental snapshots at different times. The SPH results including the free

Figure 18: The pressure field during the water entry stage after pinching off of the cavity.

Figure 19: Sketch of the two-layer sloshing case [79]. The rectangular tank with a length of $L_s = 0.57 \text{ m}$ and height of $H = 0.3 \text{ m}$.

Figure 20: The results of interfacial wave elevation η probed at WG1 with particle resolutions $h_1/\Delta x = 10$, $h_1/\Delta x = 20$ and $h_1/\Delta x = 40$.

Figure 21: The results of interfacial wave elevation η probed at WG1 (top) and WG2 (bottom) compared with experimental data [79].

Figure 22: Comparison of the sloshing wave shapes between the results of experimental snapshots [79] (left column) and the present multiphase δ^+ SPH model (right column) at $t = 1.20$ s, $t = 1.65$ s, $t = 2.10$ s, $t = 2.55$ s, $t = 3.25$ s, respectively, from top to bottom.

Figure 23: The pressure field of two-layer liquid sloshing at $t = 1.2, 1.65$ s.

601 surface and multiphase interface, show good agreement with the experimental
 602 snapshots. A smooth and accurate interface is obtained in the present work,
 603 demonstrating the capability of the current multiphase SPH model to simulate
 604 multilayer sloshing problems effectively.

605 Taking the instants $t = 1.2$ s and $t = 1.65$ s when the free surface exhibits
 606 large deformation as examples, as shown in Figure 23, the pressure field is
 607 also smoothed and without noise at the interface. Therefore, it is sufficient
 608 to demonstrate that the present SPH scheme has a good capability to handle
 609 free-surface problems.

610 Additionally, we also compare the particle distribution with the results sim-
 611 ulated with the artificial viscosity parameter $\alpha = 0.02$, as shown in Figure 24.
 612 The interface and free surface simulated with $\alpha = 0.02$ are similar to those simu-
 613 lated with $\alpha = 0.1$, and the particle distribution is uniform with no penetration
 614 occurring. It is again indicated that artificial viscosity does not play a key role
 615 in preventing interface penetration.

616 3.6. Water sloshing with entrapped air pockets

617 The air pressure predicted in the investigations is limited in the previous
 618 literature. In this subsection, the water sloshing with an entrapped air pocket,
 619 experimentally investigated by Luo et al. [80] is simulated in the present work
 620 to verify the accurate prediction of air pressure. The numerical tank setup is
 621 identical to the experiment [80] shown in Fig. 25. The tank is divided into
 622 left and right tanks connected by a short channel, each with a water depth of
 623 $d_l = d_r = 0.17$ m. The motion of the tank follows a traditional pattern [80]
 624 governed by:

$$x(t) = \begin{cases} -\frac{At}{5} \sin(\omega t), & t < 5 \text{ s} \\ -A \sin(\omega t), & t \geq 5 \text{ s}, \end{cases} \quad (21)$$

625 where A and ω are the amplitude and frequency, set as $A = 0.0412$ m, and
 626 $\omega = 3.6807$ rad/s. In this configuration, the air phase is compressed in the right
 627 tank when water sloshes from left to right, and is expanded when sloshing from

Figure 24: The particle distribution of two-layer liquid sloshing at $t = 1.65$ s, simulated with $\alpha = 0.1$ and $\alpha = 0.02$, respectively.

628 right to left inducing significant variation of air pressure. Four pressure sensors
629 are placed: p_{w1} and p_{a1} placed at the right tank to monitor the water and air
630 pressure, respectively, and p_{w2} and p_{w3} to monitor the water pressure in the
631 left tank. Notably, the left tank is connected to the atmosphere and no air is
632 trapped in it, allowing the air phase in the remaining region of the left tank to
633 be neglected. In this scenario, the capability of the present scheme to model
634 multiphase flows with free-surface can be more clearly observed. Additionally,
635 as mentioned in subsection 3.2, the present work can maintain stable pressure of
636 the air phase with the ghost boundary condition. Therefore, to further describe
637 the pressure variation of the air phase, the case of retaining the air phase in the
638 left tank (i.e. #1 shown in Figure 25) is also simulated for comparison with the
639 former setup. The fluid properties of water and air are consistent with those in
640 the previous cases.

641 As shown in Figure 26, the wave shape simulating with the present SPH
642 model shows (#2 in this case) relatively good agreement with the experimental
643 wave profiles at several time instants. As can be observed, smoothed free surface
644 is reproduced without additional treatment, illustrating the capability to
645 accurately handle free-surface in the present model.

646 Figure 27 presents the water pressure monitored at p_{w2} and p_{w3} . The impact
647 pressures on the solid wall simulating with the present multiphase δ^+ -SPH model
648 agree well with the experimental data [80].

649 Additionally, Figure 28 depicts the temporal evolution of the water and gas
650 pressures monitored at the right tank. It is noteworthy that both the SPH
651 simulation results, with or without the air phase in the left tank, show good
652 agreement with the experimental data. Upon impact on the water in the con-

Figure 25: A schematic of the tank simulated with water sloshing with an entrapped air pocket [80]. Two cases are considered: one with the remaining region filled with air phase (referred to as #1), and the other without (referred to as #2) in the left tank.

necting channel, resulting in a rise in pressure, the air pocket compresses as
 expected (see the pressure point p_{a1}). Subsequently, the air pressure influences
 the water pressure surrounding the air pocket as well (see the pressure point
 p_{w1}). Correspondingly, as shown in Figure 28, the trend of the air and water
 pressure variation observed in the right tank closely resembles each other. As
 plotted in the last row, during the sloshing process from $t = 11$ s to $t = 12$ s, the
 enlarged views of pressure variation of both air and water show good agreement
 despite some discrepancies. Furthermore, the evolution of air pressure contours
 during time $t = 11$ s to $t = 12$ s is plotted in Figure 29. As can be seen, the
 pressure of the air and the interphase are smoothed despite large density ratio.

In general, as shown in Figure 28 and Figure 29 it is sufficient to demonstrate
 the strong capability of the present SPH scheme to model the compressibility
 of air and predict real air pressure variation in multiphase flow problems.

Figure 30 presents a comparison of pressure fields between simulations with
 and without an air phase in the left tank, representing scenarios with and with-
 out a free surface, respectively. Notably, the wave profiles simulated with a free
 surface are closely consistent with those of the scenario without it. Since there
 is no air pocket in the left tank, water pressure fields are also consistent with
 each other. This is evident from the results shown in Figures 27 and 28, fully
 demonstrating the accuracy and capability of the consistent δ^+ -SPH in handling
 free surface.

4. Conclusion

In this study, we introduce a consistent δ^+ -SPH model for multiphase flows,
 expanding upon the framework outlined for single-phase flows in [41]. The
 consistent multiphase δ^+ -SPH model accounts for the compressibility of different
 phases, integrating an acoustic damper term for incompressible phases and using
 physical sound speeds for compressible phases. Distinguished from the work by
 Sun et al. [41] on single-phase flows, the proper implementation of the shifting

Figure 26: Comparison of the sloshing wave shapes between the results of the consistent multiphase δ^+ -SPH model (right column) and experiment (left column) [80].

(a) The evolution of pressure probed at point p_{w2}

(b) The evolution of pressure probed at point p_{w3}

Figure 27: The present SPH results including #1, and #2 scenarios of water pressure monitored at points p_{w2} and p_{w3} compared with experimental results [80].

Figure 28: The present SPH results (with and without air phase in the left tank) of air pressure monitored at p_{a1} and water pressure at p_{w1} compared with experimental results [80].

Figure 29: The pressure fields of right tank at several instants from $t = 11$ s to $t = 12$ s.

Figure 30: Comparison of pressure fields between simulations with (left column) and without (right column) the air phase in the left tank.

681 velocity at interfaces poses a unique challenge for multiphase problems. To
682 address this issue, we proposed new strategies for handling the $\delta\mathbf{u}$ terms at
683 multiphase interfaces, ensuring stable pressure fields for both water and air
684 without requiring a background pressure.

685 We conducted a two-phase hydrostatic test against analytical trends, demon-
686 strating the stability and accuracy of the current multiphase model. A smoothed
687 interface, as well as the particle distribution and pressure field, was obtained,
688 with the pressure profiles agreeing well with analytical results.

689 For what concerns impact flows with entrapped air problems, multiphase
690 dam breaking, slamming of LNG tank insulation panel, the cavity oscillation
691 during wedge water entry, and sloshing with entrapped air pocket test cases are
692 considered all characterized by large density ratios. In the dam breaking case,
693 unlike the δ^+ -SPH model with simple particle shifting [71], the present multi-
694 phase δ^+ -SPH model effectively accounted for air compressibility and achieved
695 stable pressure field, showing a better performance in volume conservation. In
696 the other three cases, the air pressure was qualitatively verified, and in par-
697 ticular, pressure fluctuations over short durations were accurately predicted by
698 monitoring the pressure of the entrapped air pocket or air cavity. Furthermore,
699 to demonstrate the capability of the present SPH model in modeling free sur-
700 faces in multiphase flows, we conducted two-layer liquid and sloshing with an
701 entrapped air pocket under two conditions: with and without free-surface in the
702 left tank. Both wave profiles and pressure loads on the tank were consistent,
703 showing the capability to solve with free-surface in multiphase scheme.

704 The good capability of the present SPH model in modeling the compress-
705 ibility of different phases was well discussed. We expect to extend the present
706 multiphase SPH scheme to applications involving violent flows with entrained
707 air, such as violent wave impact on structures.

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720

721 **Appendix A. Enumeration tests: two strategies for the treatment of**
 722 **$\delta\mathbf{u}$ -terms in continuity equation applied at interfaces**

723 We proposed two strategies for handling $\delta\mathbf{u}$ -terms in the continuity equation,
 724 specifically, the strategy $\ast 1$ refers to Eq. 18 and the strategy $\ast 2$ refers to Eq.
 725 19 for $\delta\mathbf{u}$ -terms in the continuity equation as discussed in Subsection 2.4. Here,
 726 through cases of two-phase hydrostatic and dam-break scenarios, we evaluate the
 727 performance of the two strategies at interfaces, including fluid-solid and multi-
 728 fluid interfaces. Notably, in the present SPH, strategy $\ast 1$ is applied at fluid-solid
 729 interfaces and the strategy $\ast 2$ at multi-fluid interfaces, showing stable behavior
 730 (labeled as \ominus). Four modes discussed for $\delta\mathbf{u}$ -terms treatment at interfaces are
 731 listed in Table A.2.

Table A.2: Modes of different strategies for handling $\delta\mathbf{u}$ -terms in the continuity equation at the interfaces. Strategy $\ast 1$ refers to Eq. 18 and strategy $\ast 2$ refers to Eq. 19.

Mode	Fluid-solid interface	Multi-fluid interface
1	$\ast 1 \ominus$	$\ast 1 \ominus$
2	$\ast 2 \ominus$	$\ast 2 \ominus$
3	$\ast 2 \ominus$	$\ast 1 \ominus$
4 (Present SPH)	$\ast 1 \ominus$	$\ast 2 \ominus$

732 **• Comparison of two strategies applied at multi-fluid interface**

733 We first compare the two strategies applied at the multi-fluid interface, with
 734 the strategy $\ast 1$ used at the fluid-solid interface. In other words, the comparison
 735 is between Mode 1 and Mode 4 (i.e. present SPH).

736 In hydrostatic scenarios, Figure A.31 shows the pressure distribution along
 737 the tank centerline at $t(g/H_w)^{1/2} = 40$. Both Mode 1 and Mode 4 (that is,
 738 the current SPH adopted) achieve accurate pressure distribution and maintain
 739 the background pressure. Strategy $\ast 1$ may be a potential alternative for the
 740 multi-fluid interface. However, as shown in Figure A.32, results with Mode 1
 741 show particle clustering at the interfaces, while the present SPH (using strategy
 742 $\ast 2$ at multi-fluid interfaces) results in more uniform particle distribution and
 743 stable background pressure.

744 In cases of violent impacts, the use of strategy $\ast 1$ exhibits unstable behavior
 745 at multi-fluid interfaces, especially instability caused by splashing of fluid par-
 746 ticles during large interface deformation. Using the dam-breaking benchmark
 747 as an example, Figure A.33 compares particle distributions between Mode 1
 748 and Mode 4 (that is, the present SPH adopted) at instant $t(g/H)^{1/2} = 10.78$.
 749 In Mode 1, splashing water particles are "entrapped" by air particles, leading
 750 to chaotic interfaces (\ominus), and then causing pressure instability, while Mode 4
 751 maintains uniform particle distribution and smoothed pressure field. Therefore,
 752 strategy $\ast 2$ is the preferred choice for multi-fluid interfaces, especially in violent
 753 impact scenarios.

Figure A.31: The pressure distribution of two-phase hydrostatic at $t(g/H_w)^{1/2} = 40$ simulated with four modes respectively.

Figure A.32: The particle distribution of two-phase hydrostatic simulated with Mode 1 and present multiphase δ^+ -SPH.

Figure A.33: Comparison of pressure fields and particle distribution (enlarged view) at multi-fluid interfaces simulated with Mode 1 and the present multiphase δ^+ -SPH.

Figure A.34: Comparison of pressure fields and particle distribution (enlarged view) at fluid-solid interfaces simulated with Mode 2 and Mode 3.

754 • **Comparison of two strategies applied at fluid-solid interface**

755 Regarding the treatment of $\delta\mathbf{u}$ -terms at fluid-solid interfaces, Figure A.31,
756 shows that applying strategy *2 (i.e., Mode 2 and Mode 3) leads to unstable
757 pressure in the simulation of two-phase hydrostatic simulations. Furthermore, in
758 the dam-breaking scenario shown in Figure A.34, when the water body with high
759 velocity is about to impact the solid wall, severe instability arises at the fluid-
760 solid interfaces, resulting in unstable pressure fields and particle penetration
761 with Mode 2. Similar results are observed simulated with Mode 3, further
762 confirming that the strategy *2 shows poor behavior at fluid-solid interfaces
763 (⊖). Simulations with Mode 2 and Mode 3 fail before water impacting the solid
764 wall. And as discussed in Section 3, using the strategy *1 has demonstrated
765 stable behavior at fluid-solid interfaces.

766 Therefore, based on the above discussion, it is recommended that strategy
767 *1 is used for fluid-solid interfaces to ensure stability, while strategy *2 is better
768 suited for handling $\delta\mathbf{u}$ -terms in the continuity equation at multi-fluid interfaces.
769

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